

Increasing acceptability of wind turbine parks in the Netherlands

University of Groningen

Date: 01-02-2018

Word count: about 5100

Individual Assignment

Designing Interventions

Faculty of Behavioural and Social Sciences

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Introduction

The goal of this paper is to analyse the issue of low acceptability of wind energy - more concisely, wind parks - within the context of local communities. Main issues are that currently fossil fuels are being used widely instead of renewable, more sustainable energy sources and this is especially true within the Netherlands. These energy sources also have a high impact on the environment, on the health of both humans and animals, they account for natural disasters and accidents, and cause economic and geopolitical issues. Furthermore, the Netherlands is lagging behind most European countries when it comes to obtaining related goals (e.g., EU2020) and faces obstacles of changing this stance, such as low acceptability of renewable energy resources. This chapter will focus on better understanding issues of non-renewable resources and obstacles of using more sustainable ones.

Step 1 – Problem: Formulating a Problem Definition

What is the at hand problem and why is it considered a problem?

Fossil fuels have a highly *negative impact* on several factors, including the environment (e.g., damages in buildings and structures, increases in air pollution levels, disruptions of aquatic ecosystems, emission of greenhouse gases and biodiversity loss), human health, animals, and the economy due to technologies related to their extraction, transportation, processing and combustion (Barbir, Veziroglu, & Plass, 1990). Their combustion is also one of the primary contributors to climate change (Environmental Protection Agency, 2018). They are also non-renewable energy sources and thus will be depleted, which is also cause for concern. The severity of this issue could be illustrated by exhaustion estimates (*Appendix A/1.*) – some of which have recently proven to be overestimated and thus had to be corrected. For example, world oil reserve estimates stood at 1150–1350 Gb (giga barrels – one billion barrels), but are now updated to count only 850–900 Gb (Owen, Inderwildi, & King, 2010). *Geopolitical* factors related to fossil fuel imports and exports could also lead to interdependency on an international scale (Scholten & Bosman, 2016).

However severe and pressing the aforementioned issues seem, fossil-based energy systems are still *widely used* within the Netherlands. According to World Data (2019), total energy consumption of the Netherlands in comparison to European average is significantly higher in every energy sector – including electricity, crude oil and natural gas consumption (*Appendix A/2.*). The production is highly reliant on fossil fuels with 80,4% of total production based on such, while renewable energy sources only account for 22% of production capacities (*Appendix A/3.*). The carbon footprint of the Netherlands is also almost two times higher than

the European average, amounting to 9.77 tonnes of CO₂ emissions per capita in 2014 (*Appendix A/4.*). Reducing reliance on fossil fuels is also proving to be a relatively slow process for the Netherlands (*Appendix A/5.*) – an objective especially important in terms of accomplishing goals set by the EU2020 climate and energy agreement. Compared to other countries, the Netherlands is lagging behind most European countries in this mission (*Appendix A/6.*).

Renewable energy resources such as geothermal, solar and wind power could be viable alternatives to fossil fuels, but despite likely positive outcomes of such an energy transition and – in some instances – reportedly strong public support for wind energy technologies, resistance of local communities often prevent or prolong the finishing of large-scale green investments (Hall & Ashworth, 2012; Steg, Berg, & Groot, 2012). Insufficient levels of acceptability of wind turbine parks and their construction is a relatively well-researched example to such issues and could lead to a wide range of unwanted effects, such as protests or even violence. Relevant to this topic, resistance surrounding the wind park projects in the Drenthe area are current, local examples of consequences of low acceptance (van Santen & Kooiman, 2018).

For whom is this a problem? Target groups

Above-mentioned examples of negative consequences of low acceptance rates are problems for not only initiators of wind park projects such as the Dutch government and investors, but also municipalities who must deal with discontent caused protests, violence or even criminal activity. Furthermore, landowners who benefit by gaining yearly rental fees for providing their lands to constructors are at risk of being targeted by opposers. Local communities and citizens also suffer consequences as within community conflicts increase during such projects due to disagreements between opposers and proposers. Based on previous research and empirical data, low acceptability could be a very important obstacle to building wind parks. Considering this influence of local acceptability on how wind turbines could be constructed, suggested target group for related interventions would consist of local communities and citizens. Aims of interventions should be to increase community/local acceptability levels of the construction of wind parks.

Problem definition

The problem definition could hence be concluded as follows: Fossil fuel-reliance is a serious issue within the Netherlands, but local communities are not always keen on accepting renewable alternatives being built within their vicinity. Which factors determine acceptability of wind turbines within local communities? How can we introduce an intervention that might help the energy transition, or, more specifically, the construction of wind parks? *Why is it*

difficult for initiators to gain the acceptance of local communities with regards to local wind park projects and how can we increase this acceptability of wind parks?

Step 2 – Analysis: Possible explanations

The intervention developed for the issue outlined above will focus on increasing acceptability of wind energy sources within local communities. Acceptability has several different definitions, with most relating to the one given by the Oxford Dictionaries, “the quality of being tolerated or allowed” (Acceptability, n.d.). It could be perceived both as an attitudinal or behavioural construct and while some studies differentiate between acceptability and acceptance on this basis (Huijts, Molin, & Steg, 2012), this paper will use these two terms interchangeably with an attitudinal focus. Acceptability is gaining increased attention with regards to renewable energy transition globally (Perlaviciute & Steg, 2014), since insufficient levels of acceptability among local communities has been proven to be an obstacle of the construction of wind turbine parks (Steg; et al., 2012). Furthermore, changes in acceptability based on a wide variety of interventions have been documented by a range of scientific articles (Rand & Hoen, 2017; ter Mors, Terwel, & Daamen, 2012; Walter, 2014).

More concisely, *community acceptance* is often the basis of resistance against constructions - it is a type of acceptability which refers to acceptance of a technological implementation by affected communities (e.g., wind turbines) (Roddis, Carver, Dallimer, Norman, & Ziv, 2018). For this reason, increasing community acceptability levels of local communities will be the target of the following research and the interventions that are to be developed. Possible explanations were mainly based on free association techniques, interviews with local opposers of the Drenthe wind project and theoretical approaches (for a more detailed explanation and description of approaches used, *see Appendix B.*). Three main theoretical explanations of acceptability are described in the following chapter.

The first explanation is a comprehensive model, named the *technology acceptance framework* (Huijts et al., 2012) which incorporates several possible explanations based on a meta-analysis of the existing literature on technology acceptance (*Figure 1.*). This framework highlights important factors influencing acceptance, including but not limited to distributive and procedural fairness, trust, perceptions about costs, risks and benefits, affect and attitude, personal and social norms. Based on an extensive literature research, authors found that trust and procedural fairness are interrelated, with some studies concluding that perceived fairness of decision-making processes lead to an increase in trust in initiators of projects dealing with new technologies, while others summarized the effect to be reversed and trust leading to a

perception of fairness. Trust in turn has an effect on affections, costs, risks and benefits related to the subject, all of which could lead to an increase of acceptance via positive attitudes and intentions to accept. While other variables are also listed and explained within the model, this paper will focus on the ones already mentioned above (for a more detailed reason for this decision, *see Appendix C.*).

Figure 1. The technology acceptance framework (Huijts et al., 2012)

The second explanation is related to the tenets of *environmental* and *energy justice*. These concepts are related to justice principles and how these could be applied in the research of the energy transition as well as the acceptability of renewable energy technologies. Also, they both incorporate three core tenets: procedural, recognition and distributional justice (Jenkins, McCauley, Heffron, Stephan, & Rehner, 2016; Kuehn, 2000).

Procedural justice refers to equal access to decision-making processes related to a distribution of goods, benefits or even risks (Jenkins et al., 2016) and has been found to be directly related to trust, and indirectly to acceptance (Huijts et al., 2012). Interviews with local citizens living near wind park construction areas (Leeuw, 2014) also point to the fact that perceived difficulties in participation and bureaucratic issues lead to an increase of mistrust.

Recognition justice is related to procedural justice but instead of referring to the equality of participation, it considers disrespectful treatment of parties involved in these processes (Jenkins et al., 2016). In this specific case it might occur when local citizens' views are mislabelled (e.g., referring to their selfishness instead of listening to their reasoning) and they are demeaned or simply their sacrifices are not recognized as such.

Distributional justice concerns the unequal allocation of benefits (in this case, benefits of wind energy), but also refers to how associated responsibilities are unevenly distributed (Jenkins et al., 2016). Local communities near wind parks might feel that they have to bear a disproportionate amount of risks and costs, without a proper amount of benefits being assigned to them, and this might lead to feelings of injustice, and, indirectly, lower acceptance of such projects. Since perceived justice and fairness have been linked on multiple occasions to acceptability (Huijts et al., 2012; Rand & Hoen, 2017), these two interrelated justice frameworks could serve as a theoretical basis of exploring perceived injustice related to wind park acceptance.

The third explanation is based on the *social licence to operate*, a concept defined as an ongoing acceptance of a development granted by local citizens and communities (N. L. Hall, 2014). Although there are several definitions and approaches to this concept, core aspects have been formulated based on current findings (N. L. Hall, 2014). These include the notion that (1) developers should consider the initial state as one without a social licence and understand that they must engage communities to gain their trust. Furthermore, (2) they must understand that this acceptance should not only be earned, but also maintained and that (3) a SLO brings inherent values. There is also (4) a need for transparent, open dialogue between stakeholders – ideally, before announcing a project. (5) Information is also crucial, as communities must be informed to be able to make informed decisions and consider trade-offs.

Conclusively, two broader concepts seem to emerge based on these theoretical explanations: (1) Trust in initiators and (2) Perceived justice or fairness. The first explanation is based on the *technology acceptance framework* and draws attention to how trust in initiators of wind park constructions influences perceptions about risks, costs and benefits and via these it might indirectly lead to an increase in attitudes and acceptability. The second explanation – based on *environmental* and *energy justice* - conceptualizes how perceptions of fairness in processes, recognition and distribution are linked to trust and could lead to an increase in attitudes towards the construction of wind parks. This line of thought is complemented by the *social licence to operate framework*, which outlines within its core aspects some guidelines related to procedures and decision-making processes which – when applied – might lead to an increase in acceptance. All concepts outlined above are interrelated but still add to the understanding of acceptability by adding valuable information about psychological variables that are directly and indirectly related to acceptability. For example, without basic information on decisional processes of local wind parks (as outlined by the SLO framework), citizens are less likely to view processes as transparency and are not able to participate in these even if they

are interested in doing so. This could lead to increased feelings of injustice and a lack of perceived fairness (relating to environmental/energy justice), which in turn would also mean a decrease of trust in initiators (based on the technology acceptance framework).

Step 3 – Test: Developing and testing the process model

Next, based on previously described theoretical and empirical approaches, a process model was developed and tested. As research on acceptability within this context is fragmented, multiple studies on acceptability of not only wind turbines, but more broadly, renewable resources, technological developments and the construction of risky energy sources have been reviewed. Reoccurring psychological constructs that have been found to influence acceptance have been gathered and reflected on from the perspective of the target group (local communities and citizens), sometimes changed based on this, and then integrated into the model. Most important variables incorporated in the final model have been selected based on existing literature cited within this paper, but also on interviews conducted with community members of a wind park siting located in the Drenthe area (*see Appendix B/2*). The strengths of relationships between psychological constructs will be displayed by standardised regression coefficients (beta weights) based on how relevant resources describe relationships using these. As a result stemming from above, the process model consists of six indirect and direct variables, which are predictors of “community acceptability of local wind parks” (*see Figure 2.*). Acceptability will be measured with two items (*see Appendix E/1.*) adapted from a study on mining acceptability (Lacey, Carr-Cornish, Zhang, Eglinton, & Moffat, 2017).

Figure 2. Proposed process model

Perceived risks (i.e. risks linked to wind turbines by local citizens) are assumed to have a direct negative relationship with community acceptability. Several studies (Huijts et al., 2012; Rand & Hoen, 2017) and interviews with local citizens (Leeuw, 2014) found that concerns regarding risks of wind turbines are indeed related to the acceptability of wind turbine siting.

In the context of accepting risky energy sources, acceptance of nuclear power energy has been found to be negatively ($\beta = -.275$, $p < 0.001$) linked to perceptions about risk (Ryu, Kim, & Kim, 2018). Perceived risk is also known as a mediator between trust and acceptability energy transitions, with a higher level of trust leading to less perceived risk and in turn, to higher levels of acceptance (Steg, Perlaviciute, & van der Werff, 2015). Perceived risks will be measured with questions (*see Appendix E/2.*) based on a similar study conducted by Midden and Huijts (2009).

Perceived benefits (i.e. benefits linked to wind turbines by local citizens) are assumed to have a positive relationship with community acceptability. Several related studies found this relationship to be true in the case of acceptability of wind turbine projects (Huijts et al., 2012; Wolsink, 2007), and specific effect sizes of benefits affecting acceptability could be estimated ($\beta = .65$, $p < 0.01$) based on a study testing this relationship in the context of acceptability of carbon dioxide captures (Terwel, Harinck, Ellemers, & Daamen, 2009). Perceived benefits will be measured with questions (*see Appendix E/3.*) based on a similar study conducted by Midden and Huijts (2009).

Trust (i.e. belief in the reliability of wind park initiators and constructors) is assumed to have both a direct and an indirect effect on acceptability via perceived risks and benefits. Trust has been outlined as one of the most important factors in such cases by multiple studies (Ellis & Ferraro, 2016; Huijts et al., 2012; Perlaviciute & Steg, 2014; Walter, 2014), with it affecting perceptions about risks and benefits in a study on trust in organizations involved in the management of new technologies (Terwel et al., 2009). The affect described in this study has a different effect size based on the type of trust measured, with integrity-based trust (i.e. trust based on the honesty and openness of an organization) having a smaller (if even detectable) effect on both perceived risks ($\beta = -.05$, nonsignificant) and benefits ($\beta = .34$, $p < .10$). Meanwhile, competence-based trust (i.e. trust based on the expertise and experience of an organization) proved to have a significant effect on perceived risks ($\beta = -.61$, $p < .01$) as well as perceived benefits ($\beta = .88$, $p < .01$).

Based on this distinction and the difference between the effect sizes of the two concepts, competence-based trust seems to be especially important in this case. Since both types of trust are integrated in the broader definition provided above and only the two components together seem to fit all other relationships displayed in the model, the broader definition will be used, and both aspects will be kept in mind. Trust hence will be measured with two statements (*see Appendix E/4.*) adapted from related studies (Connelly, Crook, Combs, Ketchen, & Aguinis, 2018; Lee, 2004).

Perceived treatment fairness (i.e. perceived respectful treatment of local citizens involved in these projects) is based on recognition justice as outlined above and interactional fairness (see Appendix B.). This construct is assumed to have a direct positive effect on trust and an indirect positive relationship to acceptability. Since it is a fairly new concept, similar constructs were sought out and found in the form of contact quality. Contact quality refers to perceptions of local citizens on how they are being treated and is proven to be directly positively related to trust ($\beta = .40, p < .001$) in the context of community acceptance of mining (Moffat & Zhang, 2014). This integrated variable will be measured by questions (see Appendix E/5.) adapted from Moffat and Zhang (2014).

Perceived procedural fairness (i.e. perceived fairness of decisional processes related to wind turbine construction) is cited in several studies as a main contributor to acceptability (Perlaviciute & Steg, 2014; Rand & Hoen, 2017; Walter, 2014). It is assumed to have a direct effect on trust and through that, an indirect effect on acceptability based on a study on acceptability of mining by Lacey, Carr-Cornish, Zhang, Eglinton, and Moffat (2017) which describes a positive relationship between procedural fairness and trust ($\beta = .46, p < .001$). Based on and adapted from the same study, this construct will be measured with two items (see Appendix E/6.).

Perceived distributional fairness (i.e. perceived fairness of the distribution of costs and benefits related to wind turbine construction) is assumed to have a direct effect on trust and an indirect effect on acceptability based on a study on acceptability of mining by Lacey, Carr-Cornish, Zhang, Eglinton, and Moffat (2017) which describes a positive relationship between distributional fairness and trust ($\beta = .36, p < .001$). Perceived distributional fairness will be measured with questions based on the same study (see Appendix E/7.).

Step 4 – Help: Developing interventions

Different aspects of *perceived fairness* are regarded in the proposed process model and although they refer to distinct concepts, their modifiability and effect sizes are similar. *Perceived procedural* and *distributional fairness* are considered moderately modifiable based on empirical studies that argue for the increase of these two constructs and showcase a multitude of viable, proven possibilities for this agenda (Moffat & Zhang, 2014; ter Mors et al., 2012). *Perceived treatment fairness* is assumed to be even more modifiable based on how such perceptions are mainly affected by the treatment of local citizens, which could be influenced on an interpersonal level as opposed to distributional and procedural fairness which are influenced

by large-scale processes. Based on effect sizes introduced above, procedural fairness has a large effect, while treatment and distributional fairness have moderate effect sizes.

While the modifiability of *trust* depends on perceived fairness components, it could also be described as a belief based on experiences with initiators and knowledge regarding their conduct. Since beliefs can be influenced, and this type of experience and knowledge could be easily made available, trust was noted to be moderately modifiable. Its effect size could be considered as large based on studies either directly or indirectly connecting it to acceptability (Terwel et al., 2009).

The modifiability of *perceived benefits* and *perceived risks* depend on the level of trust in initiators. Additionally, these two variables are attitudinal constructs, which – based on the Elaboration Likelihood Model – are modifiable if efforts of changing them are aligned with the characteristics of the situation and the target group (Petty, Barden, & Wheeler, 2009). Based on estimated relationships presented in the previous chapter, perceived benefits are assumed to have a large effect on acceptability, but these are dependent on trust levels (Terwel et al., 2009). Hence, in this case they have been downgraded to have a moderate effect size. Effect size of perceived risks is also dependent on trust levels. Conclusively, a balance table of all six variables could be established (*Table 1*).

	Modifiability	Effect size
Perceived treatment fairness	++	+
Perceived procedural fairness	+	++
Perceived distributional fairness	+	+
Trust (competence-based)	+	++
Perceived benefits	+/0	+
Perceived risks	+/0	+/0

Table 1. Proposed balance table

The proposed interventions will focus on three variables. The first one is “*perceived treatment fairness*”, as it has a high modifiability and a moderate effect size. Based on above mentioned studies and empirical findings, local citizens often lack the feeling of being respected and treated fairly (Moffat & Zhang, 2014), which also has an effect on their trust in initiators. The second variable is “*perceived procedural fairness*”, which has a moderate modifiability and a high effect size and is cited as an important determinant of acceptability by several studies (Huijts et al., 2012; Perlaviciute & Steg, 2014), but interviewees also mention concepts related to it (Leeuw, 2014) as factors that are responsible for decreasing their acceptance levels. It also

effects “*trust in initiators*”, which is the third variable that is considered important for interventions. Although the modifiability of trust is dependent on constructs related to perceived fairness, its effect size is high. Furthermore, since two of the aforementioned fairness variables will also be targeted, the modifiability of these interrelated concepts is assumed to increase.

Consequently, three intervention plans were developed (for an overview of these, see *Table 2.*). Interventions are based on a variety of empirical findings as well as proposed and empirically proven methods (Goldberg, Pasher, & Levin-Sagi, 2006; N. L. Hall, 2014; Jami & Walsh, 2017).

Channel	Features	Potential reach	Individual-level effect	Effect type
Brochure	Four-page leaflet with information elements, infographics and an invitation to the conference.	Local citizens (sent out to all households)	Small	New knowledge on the topic and decision-making processes, initial incentive for increasing participation in decision-making processes
Conference	Changing the experiences of local citizens about decision-making processes by changing how their communities experience informational and structural influences.	Members of the community	Small / Medium	New knowledge on the topic and decision-making processes, increase in participation and perceptions about procedural fairness
Knowledge brokers	Personal contacts during the conference and on a few separate occasions	Participants of the conference sessions, citizens requesting meetings	Medium / Large	Increase in trust, perceived treatment fairness, and participation

Table 2. An overview of proposed interventions

First, a *four-page brochure* will be sent to all households within the affected area. The brochure will have basic information on wind parks, as well as decision-making processes and possibilities of individual involvement in these. This type of active community engagement and encouragement of public participation could improve trust and perceived procedural fairness (Jami & Walsh, 2017). On the last page of the brochure, an invitation will also be displayed, inviting local citizens to the citizen-based conference “Leaders of the energy transition” – the second proposed intervention.

Second, a *citizen-based consensus conference* will be held to enable citizens to participate in the decision-making process related to local wind turbine siting. Previous research points to the efficiency of such methods when it comes to increasing citizen involvement and participation (Goldberg et al., 2006), which in turn have been found to have a positive effect on trust and perceived procedural fairness (Jami & Walsh, 2017). The conference will be held before affected areas are chosen for wind park projects, to enhance the feeling of transparency and participation in decision-making processes within local communities. The topic of the conference will be “Leaders of the energy transition”, referring to the important role that communities accepting wind parks could play in the transition to renewable energy and the main goal will be to inform and involve local citizens in planning the future of the affected area. The conference will last for three months, including three separate, two-day meetings. Meetings will have slightly different agendas, with possibilities of reiterating important informational elements (for a detailed overview of the three sessions, *see Appendix F/1.*). During the timeframe between meetings, citizens will be encouraged to participate in online discussions and conduct individual learning on the topic.

Third, independent *knowledge-brokers* (i.e. mediators who are able to facilitate collaborative problem resolution and decision-making processes through analysis and communication (Jami & Walsh, 2017)) will also be introduced. Studies reveal that a lack of trusted information combined with a lack of neutral sources could impair processes and decrease trust (Ellis, Barry, & Robinson, 2007). Hence knowledge-brokers could serve as trusted, neutral parties that convey information during the conference sessions, but also in-between. They will address local citizens in a trustworthy, attentive manner, give information, as well as ask for opinions and concerns. Their availability for citizens concerned about related issues could assure increases in perceptions regarding treatment and procedural fairness.

Step 5 – Implementation: Evaluation plan

The proposed interventions can be *pre-tested* using a focus group, which will consist of about 30-50 members to mimic a smaller version of the conference proposed. Participants will be invited in the same manner, by the four-page brochure described above, participate in three, one-day sessions of the conference and also have the ability of contacting a knowledge-broker between sessions (sessions will occur in two-week periods to mimic the conference setting in a shorter time period). They will also meet representatives and conduct a final report, as proposed in the original interventions. Psychological constructs proposed in the process model will be measured before and after the pre-test (after the final session) and short questionnaires (with

open-ended questions and Likert scales) on the content of the interventions will also be provided to participants. They will be asked to assess their liking and understanding of the topics covered during the pre-test. After finishing the questionnaire, the complete process can be discussed in a standard focus group setting so that participants can better elaborate their feedback.

Actors to be involved include local citizens, representatives (from NGOs, decision-makers from the municipality, potential initiators and the government), experts, proposers of wind parks from the local community and other communities, knowledge-brokers, a contact person for the location (a community house would be ideal), and a copy shop for the brochures. All actors must become acquainted with the schedule of the conferences, its content, goals and expectations. First of all, local citizens have to receive the brochures as they will serve as promotion for the event as well as invitations, and knowledge-brokers should also be consulted in the earliest stages. Local proposers who are motivated to help initiators will be asked to sign up to give a presentation during the last session after the first and second sessions have concluded. Proposers from the local community as well as those from other communities should be guided and helped to prepare their presentations so that they can communicate their ideas efficiently and in line with other elements of the conference sessions. A lack of interest from local citizens could become barrier of the intervention as this might inhibit a meaningful conversation between stakeholders.

Next, knowledge-brokers should be especially prepared to answer a wide range of questions related to wind parks and renewable energy in general. They should also have good interpersonal skills and be considered trustworthy – these requirements should be pre-tested before hiring the right brokers. After selecting the best people for this job, every detail should be discussed with them, since they will be there at every step of the interventions.

Additionally, the contact person for the location of the conference should be contacted and a location fitting the needs and anticipated size of the conference should be booked in advance. Those who are to present on the conference should also be contacted and advised about questions that need to be addressed. Requirements and expectations about transparency should also be communicated to representatives so that they can adjust their communication style accordingly and provide information regarding decision-making processes (which are to be partly displayed on the brochures, but also serve as a basis for knowledge-brokers).

A copy shop should also be contacted to place an order for the brochures and the printed invitations on time. The designs should also be sent, and the expected outcome should be discussed.

Finally, the government and investors – who are the financiers of the project – should be actively informed about all steps and any further requirements in a timely manner. They should be prepared to take the opinions of local citizens into consideration and base their decision on these. They should also be prepared to work closely with other actors (especially knowledge-brokers) and to issue compensations for local citizens based on what is discussed during the conference. The budget of the project should also be discussed in advance so that negotiations with external parties (e.g., copy shop and knowledge-brokers) will be in line with the budget.

Effect evaluation will be conducted based on pre- and post-intervention testing, as well as using a control group. Based on possible wind park locations, one community will be selected at random for the intervention and another – ideally within the same municipality and with similar attributes (e.g., population, demographic structure) – as the control group. A pre-test will be conducted one month before the intervention, ideally measuring all variables mentioned in the process model, but at least the outcome variable (community acceptability of local wind parks), perceived treatment and procedural fairness, and trust (all three related to the government and hypothetical initiators of a local wind park project). After the interventions, two post-tests will be administered, the first immediately after the last session of the conference to measure immediate effects, the second three months later, to measure long(er)-term effects. Tests will be administered in both the intervention and control group.

Cost evaluation should be based on long-term expectations and effects of the interventions. Notably the proposed conferences knowledge-brokers could prove to be quite expensive, with main costs including monthly wages for the knowledge-brokers (since they will be employed almost full-time), hourly wages for the experts and representatives and the potential costs of the location of the conference. However expensive this might seem initially, costs would be infinitesimal compared to the costs of the wind park project. This would be especially true when compared to an unsuccessful project where money gets poured into licencing and other costs, but a low acceptability rate inhibits the completion of the construction.

Furthermore, the interventions would also have a good ROI (return on investment) based on how in case of their success, they could be implemented in other, similar settings in an even more cost-efficient way based on the experiences of this first project. Pre-testing would also assure that the effectiveness of the project will be more precisely evaluated against its costliness.

Moreover, based on the extensive literature research, these interventions are expected to be especially effective compared to other possible interventions, thus investments in less

costly but possibly also less effective solutions might turn out to be very expensive in the end. Looking at the issue of fossil-fuel depletion, the prices of non-renewable energy sources are expected to increase steeply in the near future, hence a successful transition to renewables will lead to a reduction of costs. Conclusively, in the long-term, interventions proposed will reduce overall costs and prove to be more sustainable.

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Appendices

Appendix A - Possible further background information on the problem

Appendix A/1. Predicted rates of global fossil fuel depletion (Stephens et al., 2010)

Appendix A/2. Energy consumption per person, red line: the Netherlands, blue line: World average (World Development Indicators, 2018)

Appendix A/3. Production capacities per energy source (World Data, 2019)

Energy source	total in the Netherlands	percentage in the Netherlands	percentage in Europe	per capita in the Netherlands	per capita in Europe
Fossil fuels	238.48 bn kWh	80,4 %	48,9 %	13,919.30 kWh	8,014.87 kWh
Nuclear power	4.15 bn kWh	1,4 %	7,6 %	242.38 kWh	1,247.99 kWh
Water power	296.61 m kWh	0,1 %	24,1 %	17.31 kWh	3,946.70 kWh
Renewable energy	65.25 bn kWh	22,0 %	15,7 %	3,808.76 kWh	2,571.37 kWh
Total production capacity	296.61 bn kWh	100,0 %	100,0 %	17,312.56 kWh	16,405.51 kWh

Appendix A/4. Carbon footprint of the Netherlands compared to Europe (World Data, 2019)

	CO2 emissions in 2014	Netherlands per capita	Compared to Europe per capita
total	167.30 m t	9.77 t	5.39 t
> of which diesel + gasoline	67.00 m t	3.91 t	2.22 t
> of which natural gas	66.04 m t	3.85 t	1.31 t
> of which coal	33.26 m t	1.94 t	1.72 t
> other sources	997,424.00 t	0.06 t	0.14 t

Appendix A/5. Total and relative reduction in gross inland fossil fuel use (per year, in 2016) (European Environment Agency, 2018)

Appendix A/6. Actual and approximated share of energy from renewable energy sources in the EU member states (European Environment Agency, 2018)

Appendix B - Report on each of the methods to generate explanations

Divergent stage: list of methods used to generate explanations mentioned within the paper

- Free association
 - Problem associations
 - NIMBY: “Not in my backyard” attitudes
 - Disbelief:
 - They might not believe that wind turbines are necessary or the best resolution to the issue.
 - They might not believe that fossil fuel-reliance is an issue
 - They might not believe that climate change is indeed an issue.
 - Environmental concerns:
 - Concerns about wildlife (birds and bats)
 - Concerns about landscape change
 - Health concerns (e.g., wind turbine syndrome)
 - Economical concerns
 - Return on investment → will the turbines be beneficial in the long run?
 - A decrease in property values due to the parks
 - Decrease in tourism revenues and hence business incomes
 - Social norms: local communities less accepting because it is not within their social norms to accept wind parks
 - Knowledge deficit: they might not know enough about benefits and costs/risks
 - Distrust in initiators
 - Distrust in the government
 - Distrust in local/international investors
 - They might not consider the fact that they have to cope with possible risks fair → perceived fairness and social dilemmas
 - Conceptual associations – Conceptually similar phenomena
 - Implementation of new, unknown (renewable) technologies
 - Siting risky or otherwise unwanted constructions (e.g., mining facilities, waste disposal units, nuclear power plants)

- Perspective taking - From the perspective of local citizens
 - Unfair that their concerns are not listened to
 - Freedoms and rights related to their living spaces seemingly taken away
 - Talked down to based on expert positions instead of being listened to their concerns
- Interview/observations
 - Interviews with members of local communities that were affected by wind park siting were also used based on a study conducted by Leeuw (2014).
 - One particularly relevant case was examined in detail; the case of the Drenthe wind park project. In this case, opposition of local citizens was unheard by decision-makers and hence not only did it not decrease, people became more and more infuriated. This in turn lead to the emergence of protests, violence and some even committed arson against those involved in the project.
 - The following table summarizes main concerns of local citizens and outlines their reasoning related to these concerns (Leeuw, 2014)

Appendix B/1. Table of concerns

Concerns	Reasoning
Sustainability	Inconsistent energy production, negative returns of investment after lifespan is over (costs)
Need for wind energy in reduction of CO ₂	Alternatives not given a proper look
Reduced liveability of area	Fear: depreciation of dwellings, declining population (bad for local businesses, tourism)
Impacts on health	Noise levels allowed deemed too high. Proposers claim: addressed properly (citing research and legislation), opposers disagree (risks)
Wildlife concerns	Effects birds and bats negatively
Choice of the Drenthe area	Offshore preferred instead, municipality: scale of development is too large
Difficulties with legislation	Fast-changing rules and laws, several structures involved, perceived high levels of bureaucracy, mistrust
Social impact	Tensions: farmers (involved) versus other inhabitants (opposed) → farmers do not care for them → vandalism, threats, protests against them
Discussion should not be an economic one	Should not be an economic discussion while affecting people's area of residence so heavily - stakeholders should address "real" questions
Landscape quality	Changes in what locals are used to, but: not an important issue if the need for wind energy is satisfactorily motivated
Communication	Initiators not accurate enough regarding the plans

- Observations – mainly based on media sources on the Drenthe project
 - Unheard concerns turning into violence and protests: <https://www.nrc.nl/nieuws/2018/07/27/begin-in-het-noorden-niet-over-windmolens-a1611448>
 - Other related issues occur: <https://www.dvhn.nl/drenthe/Protest-tegen-windparkroute-%E2%80%98Dit-is-verre-van-ideaal%E2%80%99-zegt-de-wethouder-24076190.html>
 - Protests: <https://www.dvhn.nl/drenthe/Politie-steekt-stokje-voor-Drents-protest-tegen-windmolens-21681576.html>
 - Website of protesters with a lot of concerns listed: <http://www.platformstorm.nl/>

- Social psychological theories
 - o Topical strategy
 - Literature on concerns regarding wind parks – based on a related study, often emphasized concerns of local citizens (Rand & Hoen, 2017) have been paired with the concerns cited by interviewees cited above (Leeuw, 2014). Based on this, the table was completed with factors generally accountable for a decrease in acceptability:

Appendix B/2. Table of concerns and theoretical backgrounds

Concerns	Reasoning	Background
Sustainability	Inconsistent energy production, negative returns of investment after lifespan is over (costs)	<i>anticipated economic effects</i>
Need for wind energy in reduction of CO ₂	Alternatives not given a proper look	<i>issues of fairness, participation and trust</i>
Reduced liveability of area	Fear: depreciation of dwellings, declining population (bad for local businesses, tourism)	<i>anticipated economic effects</i>
Impacts on health	Noise levels allowed deemed too high. Proposers claim: addressed properly (citing research and legislation), opposers disagree (risks)	<i>concerns about health risks and safety</i>
Wildlife concerns	Effects birds and bats negatively	<i>environmental concern</i>
Choice of the Drenthe area	Offshore preferred instead, municipality: scale of development is too large	<i>issues of fairness, participation and trust</i>
Difficulties with legislation	Fast-changing rules and laws, several structures involved, perceived high levels of bureaucracy, mistrust	<i>issues of fairness, participation and trust</i>
Social impact	Tensions: farmers (involved) versus other inhabitants (opposed) → farmers do not care for them → vandalism, threats, protests against them	<i>issues of fairness, participation and trust; bribery</i>
Discussion should not be an economic one	Should not be an economic discussion while affecting people's area of residence so heavily - stakeholders should address "real" questions	<i>"hardcore opposers", protected values</i>
Landscape quality	Changes in what locals are used to, but: not an important issue if the need for wind energy is satisfactorily motivated	<i>sound and visual impacts</i>
Communication	Initiators not accurate enough regarding the plans	<i>issues of fairness, participation and trust</i>

- Community acceptance (as opposed to market and socio-political acceptance) (Roddis et al., 2018)

- Conceptual strategy
 - Acceptability of wind parks based on acceptability of new technologies: The technology acceptance framework (Huijts et al., 2012)
 - Acceptability of local mining constructions (Moffat, Lacey, Zhang, & Leipold, 2016; Moffat & Zhang, 2014)
 - Hierarchy of fairness
 - Levels of stress based in a hierarchy of perceived fairness (Greenberg, 2004) – a research based on this model lead to a better fitting one:
 - Levels of acceptance based on a hierarchy of performance appraisals (Kim & Rubianty, 2011)

Appendix B/3. Levels of acceptance based on a hierarchy of performance appraisals (Kim & Rubianty, 2011)

- General theory
 - Environmental and energy justice (Jenkins et al., 2016; Kuehn, 2000)
 - Social dilemma theory (Dawes, 1980)

Appendix C - Discuss the reduction of explanations

Overlaps:

- Fairness theories
 - Distributive and procedural fairness have been outlined as important factors in most of these theories, hence these two concepts were first focused on. There are also several studies mentioning either or both of these concepts as variables that are relevant to the issue of acceptability. There were also concerns that were raised in interviews and associations that were related to either one of these concepts. Conclusively, these two types of fairness were included in the explanations part.
 - Other types of fairness issues also emerged based on sources mentioned above. Interactional fairness and recognition justice were combined into “treatment fairness”.
- Trust
 - Proved to be an important part of the technology acceptance framework as well as most theoretical sources (e.g., related to fairness and justice).
 - Also emerged as part of or underlying reason for several concerns raised (based on interviews and associative techniques)
- Costs, risks, benefits
 - While perceived costs were also present in some frameworks and concerns, risks and benefits seemed to have a larger effect on overall outcomes of projects. Hence risks and benefits were integrated into the process model, while costs were left out.
 - Concrete concerns raised by local citizens were mostly integrated into the category of “perceived risks”
- Other variables and approaches
 - NIMBY-ism and concepts related to it were left out based on how most recent theoretical sources view it as a mere oversimplification of the issues at hand.
 - Knowledge-deficit was disregarded based on how its explanatory power is not too high. This said, knowledge and information on not the explicit topic of wind energy, but related decision-making processes could be effective ways of increasing perceived procedural fairness. Since this use of knowledge is more a

means to the goal of increasing a variable than an independent construct on its own, it has not been included as a separate psychological variable.

- Social dilemma situations do apply to the topic, but the type of dilemma described by them is assumed to be resolvable based on how some studies describe successful wind turbine siting projects. Hence focus was shifted to variables included in the process model.

Notably, other approaches could be taken, since several other variables could be included in a more comprehensive model. The decision to focus on only a few, interrelated concepts was based on theoretical and empirical approaches as well as impressions of concerns raised by interviewees related to the Drenthe wind park project.

Appendix D - Report on each of the methods to generate intervention strategies

Divergent phase:

- Direct intervention association
 - o Conveying basic information on brochures/leaflets
 - o Local meetings organized by the municipality with the goal of increasing participation and arranging meetings between different stakeholders
 - o Allowing some type of direct contact with a contact person so that questions and concerns could be addressed to someone (e.g., phelines or a representative)
- Debilitating strategies
 - o Only providing financial benefits – in previous occasions this approach proved to be inefficient (one example of this would be the Drenthe project)
 - o Only starting interventions after an area has been selected – this approach has also been proven to be faulty as local citizens can feel that they have already been left out of the most important decision
- Insights from theory: these lines of thought were described in the paper (e.g., theories regarding participation and procedural fairness)
- Insights from research
 - o Citizen-based consensus conference – this type of intervention proved to be very effective in other cases of participation building (Goldberg et al., 2006)
 - o Knowledge-brokers – also proven to be effective in cases of wind turbine projects

Convergent phase: Three possible interrelated strategies were selected based on how they are connectable and have both empirical and solid theoretical bases. Knowledge-brokers were used in successfully in similar cases and similar conferences also proved successful in case cited within the paper. Adding information elements not only on the explicit topic, but also the decision-making processes is based on the Social Licence to Operate framework which is described within the paper.

Appendix E – Measurement

Appendix E/1 – Measuring community acceptability

Participants will be asked to rate their favourability of the wind park planned to be constructed in their neighbourhood on a 7-point scale (1 = strongly not in favour, 7 = strongly in favour).

Appendix E/2 – Measuring perceived risks

Participants will be asked the following questions:

- “What do you think about the drawbacks of wind turbine parks for the whole of society?”
- “How likely do you think it is that the environment is negatively influenced by wind turbine parks?”
- “Do you expect that you yourself would be annoyed/ experience problems by a local wind turbine park?”
- “What do you think about the risks of wind turbine parks?”
- “What do you think about the risks of wind turbine parks?”
- “Do you expect that a wind turbine park in this area will influence your safety in a negative way?”
- “Do you expect that your well-being will decrease if a wind turbine park is constructed here?”.

Questions will be rated on a 7-point scale (1 = unlikely / small, 5 = likely / large)

Appendix E/3 – Measuring perceived benefits

Participants will be asked the following questions: “What do you think about the benefits of the local wind park (1) for society, (2) for yourself, (3) for the environment?”.

Questions will be rated on a 5-point scale (1 = very small, 5 = very large)

Appendix E/4 – Measuring trust

One of two statements will be focused on competence-based trust - “I believe that initiators of the local wind park project are competent to successfully achieve the goals and to realize all the promises they made to us” (Lee, 2004).

The other one on integrity-based trust – “I believe that initiators of the local wind park project keep local citizens’ best interests in mind” (Connelly et al., 2018); they will rate them on a 5-point Likert-scale (1 = strongly disagree from 5 strongly agree).

Appendix E/5 – Measuring perceived treatment fairness

Two questions will be asked from participants; they will rate them on a 5-point Likert-scale (1 = very unpleasant/negative, 5 = very pleasant/positive) how pleasant and positive their contact is with initiators of the specific wind park project (e.g., the government and those in charge of the construction).

Appendix E/6 – Measuring perceived procedural fairness

Statements will be given to participants; they will indicate how accurate they find them on a 11-point Likert-scale (0 = not describe the company at all, 5 = describes the company extremely well). Statements: “Listens well to concerns people may express about the wind park” and “Responds effectively to concerns people may express about the wind park”

Appendix E/7 – Measuring perceived distributional fairness

Statements will be given to participants; they will indicate how accurate they find them on a 11-point Likert-scale (0 = not describe the company at all, 5 = describes the company extremely well). Statements: “Initiators of the local wind park project are good at...” (1) “hiring local people”, (2) “compensating local citizens and businesses”, and (3) “providing financial support to local communities”.

Appendix F – Interventions

Appendix F/1. Timetable for the citizen-based consensus conference

Leaders of the energy transition: A citizen-based consensus conference		
Conference session 1 (two days, on a weekend)		
Preliminary considerations	During the session	After the session
Issuing a <i>brochure</i> with information about wind parks and wind energy in general. This part also outlines costs, risks and benefits so that citizens can start evaluating the trade-offs involved in such a decision. Information on decision-making processes will also be provided, reassuring citizens that the decision will be made with their contribution. The brochure is also an invitation to the conference.	Meeting and discussion with a <i>knowledge broker</i> , focusing on establishing a basic understanding of the topic and processes involved. The main goal is to start a conversation among involved stakeholders and bring together local citizens to make further conversation possible.	Participants will be asked to think about issues addressed and questions or considerations they might have about the possibility of the construction of a wind park in the area. They can send these to the knowledge broker introduced during the meeting who will respond to each inquiry but also incorporate these into the next session.
Conference session 2 (two days, on a weekend one month after the first session)		
Preliminary considerations	During the session	After the session
Sending an <i>invitation</i> to all local citizens, reminding them of the date of the next session and briefly summarizing the content of the last session.	Meeting hosted by the knowledge broker but dedicated to representatives of different stakeholders. Parties involved include the government, investors who will be working on the construction, NGOs, local interest groups and others. The goal will be to expose citizens to different perspectives about the topic and let them ask questions from the representatives. Questions and inquiries that were compiled by the knowledge broker (based on what citizens sent them) will also be presented and answered during this session. Presentations of initiators will be focused on their competences and	Participants will be again asked to think about issues and questions related to the topic, but also to consider the possibility of a local wind park project. They will be encouraged to think about and propose ideas about how risks and costs could be mitigated and benefits more equally distributed.

	expertise in wind park projects to enhance competence-based trust.	
Conference session 3 (two days, on a weekend one month after the second session)		
Preliminary considerations	During the session	After the session
Sending an <i>invitation</i> to all local citizens, reminding them of the date of the next session and briefly summarizing the content of the last session.	Proposers of wind parks from the same community and other affected communities (where wind turbines have already been constructed) will be invited to talk about their experiences ¹ and local communities can also invite a panel of experts to ask questions about a possible construction in their area. After the panel, citizens can have a discussion and then formulate their own ideas and final thoughts about the possibility of a local wind park – this they will do by making a video report and then handing that over to a representative from the government. The report should include their evaluation of proper compensation for their sacrifices ² .	The final report will be studied by decision-makers and based on that, they will formulate a proposal to the local community which citizens can vote for in a referendum.

¹ As knowledge presented by trusted parties (e.g., neighbours, community members) is likely believed (Fast & Mabee, 2015) and hence could increase trust. It is also a method that has been proven to be effective in fostering acceptance (N. Hall, Ashworth, & Devine-Wright, 2013).

² During the panel, experts will also propose possible financial incentives based on related proposals and known alternatives. This discussion and the final report could increase citizens’ sense of involvement as well as perceptions of equitable outcomes, as it is a product of consensus. This perceived equitability could also lead to higher local acceptance (Walter, 2014).